

RECYCLING POST-CONSUMER FIBREBOARD WASTE INTO NEW WOOD-BASED PANELS

PROJECT INNOVATION
FACTSHEET

Contributing to EU's circular bioeconomy, reintegrating end-of-life panels into production helps optimise wood use, extend product lifecycles, stores carbon and reduce dependence on virgin wood.

APPLICATIONS

- **Medium-density Fibreboard (MDF):** smooth surface ideal for lacquering and CNC machining. Used in furniture fronts, decorative interior fittings, wall cladding and panelling.
- **Particleboard (PB):** cost-effective, versatile, and suitable for surfacing. Used in furniture, shelving, upholstery, and flooring underlayers.

LAB RESULTS

- **MDF panels (Demo F):** incorporation of 15%-25% recycled fibres almost achieved performance of reference panels, with 15% yielding better results than 25%.
- **PB surface layer (Demo D):** integration of 20% recycled fines matched standard quality and improved surface smoothness; suitable for industrial trials. Laminate flooring.

« The EcoReFibre project explores a cascade concept to recover raw materials from waste fibreboard, which then become available for remanufacture of industrial Products.»

Prof. Stergios Adamopoulos, Coordinator
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences,
Uppsala, Sweden.

R&D CHALLENGES

- Maintaining input material quality and consistency (e.g. absence of contaminants).
- Achieving the target physical and mechanical properties.
- Scaling up the process.

NEXT STEPS

Industrial trials are planned for:

- **MDF panels (Demo F):** 15–25% recycled fibres, targeting market requirements and contaminant-free panels.
- **PB surface layer (Demo D):** Up to 20% recycled fines, with focus on machinability, surface quality, and emissions.

ECOREFIBRE AIMS
TO ESTABLISH A
CIRCULAR ECONOMY
APPROACH TO
RECYCLE WASTE
WOOD BACK
INTO
FIBREBOARDS
AND INTO NOVEL
BUILDING PRODUCTS

PARTNERS

CONTACTS

SONAE ARAUCO

Portugal | Spain | Germany | South Africa

ADELAIDE ALVES

Group R&D Director

aalves@sonaearauco.com

[sonaearauco.com](https://www.sonaearauco.com)

SLU SWEDISH UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

Department of Forest Biomaterials and Technology - Division of Wood Science and Technology | Uppsala, Sweden

Stergios Adamopoulos

Professor, Wood Science

stergios.adamopoulos@slu.se

[slu.se](https://www.slu.se)

[More information:](#)

[in EcoReFibre on LinkedIn](#)

[ecorefibre.eu](https://www.ecorefibre.eu)

This document reflects the authors' views only and neither the Agency nor the Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Photo credits: Sonae Arauco, InnovaWood.
Layout: Fovéa création.